

THE CHALLENGES AND BENEFITS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Foreign languages are shown in all pieces of the procedure for proceeding with schooling embraced in our country. Perhaps of the main issue today is to guarantee progression in the educating of foreign languages between them, for instance, at all levels, and to sort out instructing at various phases of the means of proceeding with training with a separated way to deal with the reason, content, structure, strategies and procedures.

Introduction. By the phases of the process for proceeding with instruction, we mean pre-school training, auxiliary schools, scholastic lyceums, professional schools, specialized schools, advanced education (organizations and colleges), expert's schooling, retraining and high level instructional classes. a) In our country, serious consideration is paid to training in preschool schooling establishments. This can be made sense of by the construction of the Ministry of Education around here. On the off chance that we consider the educating of foreign languages in preschool schooling establishments, it likewise requires a serious methodology, on the grounds that in this instructive foundation there are explicit highlights of foreign language educating, without which it is difficult to sort out instructing successfully. It is realized that the fundamental motivation behind showing a foreign

language in preschool training establishments is to plan learners for school.

The reasonable motivation behind showing a foreign language in preschool schooling organizations is to foster youngsters' fundamental oral discourse in a foreign language, to frame their abilities and to lay the preparation for learning an foreign language later on and, obviously, to teach them on chose subjects. In this manner, what is expected of foreign language educators is to pick foreign language showing points with a reasonable comprehension of the reason for educating, to track down ways of propelling kids to gain proficiency with a foreign language. Contingent upon the age of the preschool training establishments students, it is prudent to set the example time to 25-30 minutes. It is prescribed to utilize different shows (specialized and nontechnical),

instructional games during the preparation. Foreign language showing in auxiliary schools can be partitioned into two phases. The 1st stage can incorporate grades 1-4, and the subsequent stage can incorporate grades 5-11. In our nation, showing foreign languages generally began from the fifth grade. As of late, the progress from foreign language instructing to initially grade dislikes course readings, manuals, and educating strategies. Notwithstanding, since these issues have been settled, foreign language course books have been made for grades 1-4. In the ongoing circumstance, guaranteeing the congruity of showing materials in foreign language course readings for grades 1-11 is significant. This requires the making of bit by bit integral reading material. c) The following connection in proceeding with training is scholastic lyceums, which are auxiliary general schooling organizations that execute progression and progression of training. Scholastic lyceums contrast from optional schools in that they have countless hours dedicated to specific disciplines, and they can be coordinated under various colleges or independently. They center around unambiguous areas of social exercises and financial matters, and the disciplines are all the more firmly connected with these areas, which is the most important move towards preparing qualified experts in a specific field from here on out. Scholarly lyceum graduates can take a specific calling from here on out, expanding their insight in different resources of schools, specialized schools and colleges well defined for their field.

The educating of foreign languages in scholastic lyceums is additionally connected with this objective and requires

the formation of discrete course books in every space. These course books ought to incorporate lexical and syntactic materials and subjects connected with a specific region. While coordinating course books, educators are encouraged to consider such factors as learners' age, interests, level of information, capacities, wants, future objectives, and on this premise to rouse learners to show a foreign language. d) Vocational universities and specialized schools are instructive establishments that merit unique consideration since they train experts in every aspect of financial matters, and in this manner they contrast from instructive foundations in the past phases of proceeding with schooling.

Consequently, foreign language showing in professional universities and specialized schools ought to be connected with the future calling of the expert prepared in each instructive establishment and ought to be coordinated concerning vocation direction. The substance of instructing, that is to say, the subjects considered, lexical and syntactic material, as well as the abilities to be shaped, abilities ought to likewise be connected with the picked calling. The talking abilities to be framed are additionally expected to be connected with that calling. Learners of professional schools and specialized universities ought to have a degree of talking abilities that permits them to discuss expertly with their unfamiliar partners. This requires foreign language educators to really focus on the development of learners' proficient talking abilities and capacities in the foreign language they are learning, and to likewise sort out examples. Speech and dialogic talking abilities ought to be framed based on proficient preparation materials. e) The

primary reason for advanced education foundations is to prepare qualified experts working in all circles of social action and economy. The educating of foreign languages in establishments and colleges should be profession situated, as in professional universities and specialized schools. A particular component here is connected with the reason, content and type of showing foreign languages in instructive foundations of philological and non-philological bearing.

It is likewise important to adopt a differential strategy to the educating of foreign languages in philological instructive establishments, as there are huge contrasts between the educating of foreign languages in the resources of foreign languages and the educating of foreign languages in the resources of Uzbek and Russian. Foreign language educating at the resources of Uzbek and Russian dialects is done chiefly as reasonable classes. Learners of these resources are expected to dominate a foreign language at the degree of expert correspondence with unfamiliar partners. Appropriately, foreign language classes ought to be coordinated on the standards of informative and proficient direction. In foreign language resources, a foreign language is educated as a forte. Thusly, learners are shown the language of the specialty inside and out, both hypothetically and essentially.

Classes are led as talks, workshops, viable classes, proficient abilities and capabilities are framed at the C1 level of CEFR necessities. As of now, course books are essentially utilized for Russian-language colleges. Quite possibly of the most major problem today is the improvement of new educational plans and course books for Uzbek-speaking learners, in

view of the reason, content and present day necessities for learning a foreign language. Summing up the reason for showing foreign languages in non-philological resources, future experts prepared in these resources are expected to have the option to acquire the vital data in foreign languages from unfamiliar sources, to plan proficient articles, addresses, to speak with unfamiliar associates on proficient points. The instructive cycle ought to be coordinated for this reason. For this situation, the advancement of discrete reading material and manuals in every space of non-philological resources is perhaps of the most major problem today. These course books require the choice of expert showing materials in view of the prerequisites of the time. This fundamentally incorporates proficient subjects, their particular lexical and linguistic material. As we would see it, more consideration ought to be paid to the development of learners' perusing, interpretation and listening abilities, as a cutting edge expert ought to have the option to get proficient data from unfamiliar sources, stay informed concerning developments in this field and apply them by and by.

The following phase of proceeding with training is the graduate degree, and here, as well, recognizing two bearings: graduate degree in foreign language resources and non-philological faculties is important. Aces in the field of specialization should concentrate on a foreign language top to bottom, direct exploration on the picked subject, compose and guard an expert's paper. They likewise need to additionally extend and work on their oral and composed talking abilities and skills created in the past stages as per

the program prerequisites. Access reading up for a graduate degree at a non-philological workforce don't concentrate on a foreign language according to the perspective of specialization. A foreign language will actually want for them to have the option to get data on an examination subject of their decision from unfamiliar sources and to make sense of their perspectives at logical gatherings with the assistance of proof and to speak with unfamiliar partners on logical points.

To that end foreign language examples are coordinated as functional illustrations. A typical issue in the two region of expert's schooling is the correction of educational plans concerning proficient direction, and the division of class hours into points in light of the showing material and expert subject. It is additionally fitting to make course books and manuals for graduate learners, which will incorporate explicit highlights of every area. The last phase of proceeding with training incorporates foreign language showing in supplemental classes and retraining courses. The reason for foreign language showing in cutting edge instructional classes ought to be to illuminate experts about the most recent improvements in their field, to extend their field information, to foster proficient abilities focused on the utilization of cutting edge showing strategies and procedures practically speaking. Doing this in learning circumstances out of a feeling of shared trust, not by controlling and rebuffing the information on professionals is fitting. It would be proper to enable an

exceptionally shaped commission to control the expert abilities and information on trained professionals, to decide if they meet their calling and current necessities, and it would be fitting to follow the instructional rule of "Don't threaten, educate with interest."

During the time spent proficient turn of events, it is powerful to give proposals and exhibit practically speaking ways of applying present day instructing strategies to foreign language educating techniques. Retraining of subject matter experts, in view of the necessities of society, includes the direction of experts in related fields to a specific strength and the arrangement of them with additional information and expert abilities in this field. Showing a foreign language in retraining courses is likewise a device to accomplish this objective. The substance of foreign language educating and related lexical and syntactic material, i.e. the material ought to be coordinated in retraining courses relying upon the reason for foreign language educating.

Conclusion. To summarize, foreign language instructing at all degrees of proceeding with training ought to be in accordance with the learning targets at each level, and in light of this objective, the decision of showing content, hierarchical structure, it is expected to show strategies and procedures. Proficient preparation gives great outcomes when the instructors who arrange the preparation inspire the experts towards their calling by observing these guidelines.

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